

YIELD AND ECONOMICS OF LINSEED AS INFLUENCED BY DIFFERENT LAND CONFIGURATION AND SOWING WINDOWS

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted during *rabi* season of 2022-23 at farm of AICRP on linseed, College of Agriculture, Nagpur to study the effect of land configuration and sowing windows on yield and economics of irrigated linseed. The experiment was laid out in split plot design with four replications and fifteen treatment combinations consisting of three land configurations *viz.*, L₁ (Flat bed), L₂ (Ridges and furrow) and L₃ (Broad bed furrow) and five sowing windows S₁ (44th SMW), S₂ (45th SMW), S₃ (46th SMW), S₄ (47th SMW), S₅ (48th SMW). The results of experiment showed that significantly highest values of yield attributes like number of capsules plant⁻¹, number of seeds capsule⁻¹, test weight, seed yield ha⁻¹, straw yield ha⁻¹, GMR, NMR and B:C ratio recorded in treatment L₃ (BBF) and it was at par with treatment L₂ (Ridges and furrow). Among the various sowing windows sowing of linseed during 45th SMW (S₂) recorded highest yield attributes, GMR, NMR and B:C (2.44) ratio and it was at par with treatment S₁ (44th SMW). Interaction effect of land configuration and sowing windows found to be significant in terms of yield contributing characters like number of capsules plant⁻¹, seed yield ha⁻¹ and straw yield ha⁻¹ also in terms of NMR and it was highest in L₃S₂ (L₃ Broad bed furrow, S₂ 45th SMW)

(Key words: Linseed, oilseed crop, sowing windows, land configuration, BBF)

INTRODUCTION

Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) is an important oilseed crop of central India, locally known as jawas or alsii. It has been grown since ancient times for flax (fiber) and for seed purposes, which are rich in oil. Linseed contains a high level of lignan, and omega-3 fatty acids possess anti-cancer properties.

In recent years linseed is very much popular among the farmers of Vidarbha region. In view of the rapid spread of crop, it is important to increase the productivity of crop. Production can be increased by increasing productivity and taking additional area under cultivation. Productivity of crop can be increased by adoption of improved agronomic practices like use of suitable land configuration and sowing windows for cultivation of crop.

The proper land configuration is known for increasing moisture intake and resultant yield. Sowing of crop on broad bed and furrow, ridges and furrow are known to help linseed crop during water stress.

Optimum sowing time is one of the most important agronomic factor and non-monetary input but has noticeable impact on productivity of crop. Planting dates significantly affect growth character, yield and its components as well as oil yield in linseed. Sowing dates

have been shown to provide differential growth conditions such as temperature, precipitation and growth periods. The appropriate sowing date is very important since it ensures good seed germination, as well as timely appearance of seedling and optimum development of root system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field experiment was conducted at farm of AICRP on linseed, College of Agriculture, Nagpur during *rabi* season of 2022-23 in split plot design with fifteen treatment combinations consisting of four land configurations *viz.*, L₁- Flat bed), L₂ - Ridges and furrow and L₃ - Broad bed furrow and five sowing windows S₁- 44th SMW (Standard Meteorological Week), S₂- 45th SMW, S₃- 46th SMW, S₄- 47th SMW, S₅-48th SMW as sub plot treatments replicated four times. The crop variety PKV NL-260 was used with row to row spacing of 30 cm.

At the time of harvesting, yield attributes like number of capsules plant, number of seeds capsule, test weight (g), seed yield (kg ha⁻¹) and straw yield (kg ha⁻¹) were recorded. In order to represent the plot, five plants of linseed from each net plot were selected randomly for various biometric observations on post harvest studies. The selected five plants were labeled and all biometric observations were recorded properly on them.

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Table 1. Yield attributes, yield and economics of linseed as influenced by land configuration and sowing windows

Treatments	No. of capsules plant ⁻¹	No. of seeds capsule ⁻¹	Test weight (g)	Seed yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Total Cost of cultivation (Rs. ha ⁻¹)	Gross monetary returns (Rs. ha ⁻¹)	Net monetary returns (Rs. ha ⁻¹)	B:C ratio
Land Configuration									
L ₁ - Flat Bed	52.43	7.49	7.31	730	1366	19270	37844	18574	1.96
L ₂ - Ridges and furrow	61.25	8.07	7.39	850	1474	19770	43998	24228	2.23
L ₃ - Broad bed furrow	63.62	8.17	7.39	872	1519	19770	45119	25349	2.28
SE (m) ±	0.79	0.15	0.01	12	18	-	-	625	-
CD at 5%	2.36	0.44	0.03	35	54	-	-	1869	-
Sowing windows									
S ₁ - 44 th SMW	64.00	8.27	7.41	881	1523	19270	45593	25989	2.37
S ₂ - 45 th SMW	66.65	8.28	7.42	910	1546	19270	47029	27425	2.44
S ₃ - 46 th SMW	60.22	8.18	7.39	841	1456	19270	43514	23911	2.25
S ₄ - 47 th SMW	54.55	7.53	7.33	748	1389	19270	38808	19205	2.01
S ₅ - 48 th SMW	50.08	7.28	7.29	706	1352	19270	36658	17055	1.90
SE (m) ±	1.08	0.11	0.005	11	15	-	-	530	-
CD at 5%	3.10	0.31	0.014	32	44	-	-	1580	-
Interaction									
SE (m) ±	1.87	0.19	0.008	18	26	-	-	918	-
CD at 5%	5.59	-	-	53	77	-	-	2745	-
GM	59.10	7.91	7.37	817	1453	19395	42320	22717	2.18

Table 2. Interaction effect of land configuration and sowing windows on number of capsules plant⁻¹, seed yield, straw yield and NMR

Treatments	No. of capsules plant ⁻¹	Seed yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Net monetary returns (Rs. ha ⁻¹)
L ₁ S ₁	54.35	771	1445	20738
L ₁ S ₂	56.00	779	1402	21069
L ₁ S ₃	54.40	744	1348	19265
L ₁ S ₄	51.90	700	1326	17043
L ₁ S ₅	45.50	654	1312	14755
L ₂ S ₁	69.00	936	1560	28623
L ₂ S ₂	70.00	964	1607	30059
L ₂ S ₃	60.75	872	1475	25293
L ₂ S ₄	55.25	756	1401	19438
L ₂ S ₅	51.25	724	1326	17728
L ₃ S ₁	68.65	937	1564	28608
L ₃ S ₂	73.95	986	1629	31148
L ₃ S ₃	65.50	908	1546	27174
L ₃ S ₄	56.50	789	1441	21133
L ₃ S ₅	53.50	740	1418	18683
SE(m) ±	1.87	18	26	918
CD at 5%	5.59	54	78	2754

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of land configuration

Data revealed that application of land configuration influenced the yield attributes *viz.*, number of capsule plant⁻¹, number of seeds capsule⁻¹, test weight, seed yield ha⁻¹, straw yield ha⁻¹. Application of broad bed furrow (L₁) recorded highest values of all yield attributes and yield of linseed. Data also revealed that highest GMR (Rs 45119 ha⁻¹), NMR (Rs 25349 ha⁻¹) and B:C ratio (2.28) were observed under treatment L₃ (BBF) and it was at par with treatment L₂ (Ridges and furrow). This might be due to cumulative effect of improvement of yield attributes like number of capsule plant⁻¹, number of seeds capsule⁻¹, test weight which reflects higher yield. The results are in close conformity with Patil *et al.* (2011), who reported that application of BBF helps to maintain availability of moisture for longer duration and proper root growth of plant which helps in uptake of nutrient and ultimately results in increase in seed yield. Paul (2014) also reported that furrow opening concept is beneficial to increase the yield of linseed.

Effect of sowing windows

Sowing windows significantly influenced the yield attributes and yield of linseed. Treatment S₂ (45th SMW) recorded significantly highest value of yield attributes like number of capsule plant⁻¹ (66.65), number of seeds capsule⁻¹ (8.28), test weight (7.42 g), seed yield ha⁻¹ (910 kg ha⁻¹) and straw yield ha⁻¹ (1546 kg ha⁻¹) and it was at par with treatment S₁ (44th SMW). Also found that highest GMR (Rs 47029 ha⁻¹), NMR (Rs 427425 ha⁻¹) and B:C ratio (2.44) were observed in terms of crop sown during 45th SMW. This might be due to cumulative effect of yield attributes *viz.*, number of capsules plant⁻¹, number of seeds capsule⁻¹, test weight turned into highest yield. Raundal (2015) reported that sowing of linseed during 45th SMW was favourable to high seed production because post anthesis period coincide with the relatively low temperature. Chopra and Badiyala (2016) also observed that as sowing delays yield of linseed decreases. Jiotode *et al.* (2017) reported that early sown crop received favorable weather conditions for longer duration in terms of cool winter period which helps in pollination, pollen development and seed setting during reproductive stages which reflects higher yield. Similar results were also reported by Gopale *et al.* (2022), who reported that crop sown during 30th October faced favorable environment for growth while delayed sown crop exposed to higher temperature and water deficit condition during reproductive stages leads to lower yield. The result are in

close conformity with Kumhare *et al.* (2022), who reported that crop sown during 44th SMW having highest seed yield which might be due to optimum temperature prevailed during flowering which resulted in lower flower drop and more seed setting.

Interaction effect

Interaction effect of land configuration and sowing windows was found to be significant in terms of number of capsule plant⁻¹, seed yield ha⁻¹, straw yield ha⁻¹ and NMR. Treatment L₃S₂ (L₃-Broad bed and furrow, S₂- 45th SMW) recorded highest number of capsules plant⁻¹ and it was at par with treatment L₂S₂ (L₂-Ridges and furrow, S₂-45th SMW), L₂S₁ (L₂-Ridges and furrow, S₁- 44th SMW) and L₃S₁ (L₃-Broad bed and furrow, S₁- 44th SMW). In case of seed yield and straw yield treatment L₃S₂ recorded highest seed yield and straw yield (kg ha⁻¹) and it was at par with treatment L₂S₂, L₃S₁ and L₂S₁. In terms of NMR treatment L₃S₂ recorded highest NMR and it was at par with treatment L₂S₂, L₂S₁ and L₃S₁. Linseed sown at 45th SMW by BBF method gave net monetary returns of Rs. 31148. Therefore, it may be recommended that sowing of linseed by BBF method during 45 SMW is found beneficial.

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